

GS 82 SVT
DMS01 E480/N3077
0° → 3077E

4/11/82

①
V 95.2247
H 198.8247
SD 12.551 } 12.549
12.548 }
D 12.513

②
V 91.2961
H 154.660
SD 16.403
16.401
D 16.249

③
H 153.251
V 93.3915
SD 12.586
12.581
D 12.513

④
H 1926
101.2144
V 100.0962
91.964
SD 5.884
8.148 } 8.144
8.141 }
8.079

⑤
H 40.0058
V 95.634
SD 12.945
12.944
D 12.42

⑥
H 19.6469
V 99.1429
SD 25.746
D 25.743

⑦
H 15.6215
V 99.5271
SD 30.934
30.872 } 30.874
30.876 }
D 30.873

⑧
H 145.7928
V 100.7505
SD 19.323
19.325
D 19.323

⑨
H 134.2294
V 97.5609
SD 19.644
21.064
D 21.098

⑩
H 91.1838
V 98.81742
SD 20.061
20.060
D 20.057

⑪
H 81.2352
V 99.155
SD 18.4682 } 18.469
18.470 }
D 18.467

⑫
H 75.7644
V 95.0972
SD 14.502
14.501
D 14.47

⑬
H 70.0606
V 93.5702
SD 11.608
11.606
D 11.548

⑭
H 110.5018
V 98.9864
SD 20.365
20.364
D 20.361

⑮
H 132.5991
V 97.0777
SD 25.016
14.985
14.984
D 14.968

⑯
H 14.5111
V 100.0922
SD 15.538 } 15.534
15.531 }
D 15.5339

⑰
H 30.5828
V 96.6925
SD 29.924
31.458 } 31.459
31.460 }
D 31.410

⑱
H 19.5498
V 100.0246 } 97.2562
97.2562 }
SD 32.521 } 32.5115
32.502 }
D 32.481